

Syntheses of Mannich Bases from Benzofuran Derivatives

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Mannich bases have been prepared from methyl 5 hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate and methyl 6 hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate using different primary and secondary amines. Their structures have been proved by converting them into the compounds of known structures. Mannich bases have been also prepared from methyl 5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate and methyl 6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate through their chloromethyl derivatives.

The review of the literature shows that a few studies have been made previously on the preparation of Mannich bases from benzofuran derivatives. Kumar and Joshi¹ prepared the Mannich bases from ethyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylbenzofuran-2-carboxylate. Grinev and Venetseva² prepared the bases from 2-methyl-3-carboethoxy-5-hydroxybenzofuran and its 2-phenyl analog. However, the attempts to synthesise oxazino derivatives from benzofurans have not been made so far.

Methyl 5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (I) on condensation with paraformaldehyde and benzylamine in molar ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 yielded a product to which methyl 2'H-3'-benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-3-methyl-1',3'-oxazino-5',6',4,5-coumarilate structure (A) has been assigned as the product was insoluble in alkali and on treatment with alcoholic hydrochloric acid it gave methyl 4-benzylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate. This was further subjected to the Sommelet reaction when methyl 4-formyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate³ was obtained as seen by direct comparison.

The ester (I) on condensation with paraformaldehyde and dimethylamine in equimolecular quantities gave a compound to which the methyl 4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate structure has been assigned because on treatment with hexamethylene tetramine it gave the 4-formyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate³. The ester (I) was similarly condensed with piperidine and morpholine and the 4-substituted aminomethyl derivatives obtained were subjected to Sommelet reaction to furnish the corresponding 4-formyl derivative³.

Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (II) on Mannich reaction with paraformaldehyde and benzylamine in 1 : 2 : 1 proportion gave a compound to which methyl 2'H-3'-benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-3-methyl-1',3'-oxazino-5',6',7,6-coumarilate structure (B) has been assigned, as the product was insoluble in alkali and on treatment with alcoholic hydrochloric acid it gave hydrochloride of methyl 7-benzylaminomethyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate. This was further subjected to Sommelet reaction when methyl 7-formyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate³ was obtained as seen by direct comparison.

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1. Kumar and Joshi, *This Journal*— 1964, 737.

2. Grinev and Venetseva, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1963, 33(3), 820; *Chem. Abst.*, 1963, 59, 7466.

3. V. S. Salvi and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1968, 45(5), 439.

The ester (II) on Mannich reaction with paraformaldehyde and morpholine in equimolecular quantities gave a compound to which the methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methyl-7-morpholinomethylcoumarilate structure has been assigned because on treatment with hexamethylene tetramine it gave methyl 7-formyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate³.

It is well known that the Mannich bases can be prepared from chloromethyl derivatives. This approach has been studied in the following two cases.

The methyl ether of (I) on chloromethylation in glacial acetic acid with paraformaldehyde gave a monochloromethyl derivative to which the methyl 4-chloromethyl-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate structure has been assigned, as on treatment with hexamine in acetic acid it gave methyl 4-formyl-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate³.

The methyl 4-morpholinomethyl-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate was prepared by refluxing the 4-chloromethyl derivative with morpholine in alcohol.

The methyl ether of (II) on chloromethylation in glacial acetic acid with paraformaldehyde gave a monochloromethyl derivative to which the methyl 5-chloromethyl-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate structure has been assigned, as on treatment with hexamine in acetic acid it gave a formyl derivative which was different from the methyl 7-formyl-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate³. The methyl 5-morpholinomethyl-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate was prepared by refluxing the 5-chloromethyl derivative with morpholine in alcohol.

(A)

(B)

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Mannich bases and oxazino derivatives: Paraformaldehyde (0.005M) was dissolved in ethyl alcohol (5 ml. containing 0.1 g. potassium hydroxide) by gentle warming. The secondary amine like dimethyl amine, morpholine or piperidine (0.005M) and the hydroxy benzofuran derivative (0.005M) dissolved in ethyl alcohol (5 ml.) were added to the reaction mixture and the mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. For the preparation of the oxazino derivatives double the quantity of paraformaldehyde (0.01M) was taken and the amine used was a primary amine like benzyl amine (0.005M). The product which separated on cooling crystallised from alcohol. Melting points and analyses are recorded in the table.

TABLE

Sr No.	Name	M.P. °C	Formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen		% Chlorine	
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Methyl 2'H-3'-benzyl-3', 4'-dihydro-3-methyl-1', 3'-oxazino-5', 6', 4, 5-coumarilate	150	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	71.25	0	5.35	5.68	4.07	4.15	—	—
2.	Methyl 4-benzylamino-methyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate	143	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	69.87	70.14	5.67	5.89	4.66	4.31	—	—
3.	Methyl 4-dimethylamino-methyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate	151	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	64.28	63.86	6.49	6.51	5.67	5.32	—	—
4.	Methyl 4 piperidino-methyl-5 hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate	121	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	67.01	67.31	6.70	6.98	4.47	4.62	—	—
5.	Methyl 4-morpholino-methyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate	143	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₅ N	62.60	62.94	5.99	6.27	4.45	4.59	—	—
6.	Methyl 2'H-3'-benzyl-3', 4' dihydro-3-methyl-1', 3'-oxazino-5',6',7,6-coumarilate	124-5	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	70.87	71.20	5.88	5.68	3.71	4.15	—	—
7.	Hydrochloride of methyl 7-benzylaminomethyl-6-hydroxy-3-methyl-coumarilate	212	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ ClN	—	—	—	—	3.73	3.87	10.29	9.82
8.	Methyl 6 hydroxy-3-methyl-7-morpholino-methyl coumarilate	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₅ N	62.65	62.94	6.24	6.27	4.18	4.59	—	—
9.	Methyl 4-chloro-methyl-5-methoxy-3-methyl-coumarilate	155-7	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl	57.98	58.11	4.66	4.84	—	—	13.44	13.22
10.	Methyl 4-morpholino-methyl-5-methoxy-3-coumarilate	141-2	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	—	—	—	—	4.26	4.49	—	—
11.	Methyl 5-chloromethyl-6-methoxy-3-methyl-coumarilate	140	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl	57.62	58.11	4.47	4.84	—	—	12.83	13.22
12.	Methyl 5-formyl-6-methoxy-3-methyl-coumarilate	163-4	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₆	62.98	62.90	5.33	4.87	—	—	—	—
13.	Methyl 5-morpholino-methyl-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate	139	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	—	—	—	—	4.66	4.49	—	—

Ring opening of the Oxazino derivatives : The oxazino derivative (0.005M) in ethyl alcohol (20 ml.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (8 ml.) was heated on a steam bath for 90 min. The solution was neutralised by addition of saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The solid product obtained was crystallised from alcohol. The compounds are recorded in the table.

Chloromethylation : A mixture of the methoxy benzofuran derivative (0.01M) in acetic acid (5 ml.) and paraformaldehyde (0.02M) was treated with hydrochloric acid gas at room temperature for 30 min. The separated product was filtered and crystallised from benzene. The compounds are recorded in the table.

Sommelet Reaction : The Mannich base (0.002M) or the chloromethyl derivative (0.002M) and hexamine (0.002M) in glacial acetic acid (6 ml.) were heated for 3 hr. on a steam bath. Hydrochloric acid (10 ml., 1 : 1) was then added and the heating continued for further 30 min. The product obtained on dilution with water crystallised from alcohol. One out of these formyl derivatives was an unknown product, the analysis of which has been recorded in the table. Other formyl derivatives were confirmed by their mixed m.ps. with the known authentic samples.

Preparation of Mannich bases from chloromethyl derivatives : The chloromethyl derivative (0.002M) was refluxed with morpholine (0.002M) in alcohol (5 ml.) on a steam bath for 1 hr. The product which separated on cooling crystallised from alcohol. The compounds are recorded in the table.

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